

A topological alternative to the stellarator: plasma magnetic confinement in a knotted torus

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(Dated: July 8, 2025)

Abstract : We propose an original magnetic confinement configuration based on a knotted toroidal geometry, of the trefoil knot type, traversed by identical circular coils. This configuration, simpler than that of the stellarator, exploits the natural modulation of the magnetic field induced by the curvature of the geometry, ensuring cyclic trapping of the plasma without recourse to a poloidal field

I. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic confinement devices aim to trap hot plasma in a given volume to enable fusion reactions. The tokamak uses toroidal symmetry and imposes a poloidal component on the magnetic field to stir the particles. The more complex stellarator replaces this stirring with a calculated asymmetry of the field lines, at the cost of a heavy and difficult-to-manufacture architecture. Here we propose a radically different conceptual alternative: a knotted toroidal geometry where the modulation of the magnetic field arises solely from the local curvature of the structure. Confinement is ensured by magnetic pressure without any poloidal field.

II. GEOMETRY

The trefoil knotted curve is set by:

$$\begin{aligned}x(t) &= \sin(t) + 2 \sin(2t) \\y(t) &= \cos(t) - 2 \cos(2t) \\z(t) &= -\sin(3t)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

with $t \in [0, 2\pi]$

The knotted torus is generated by a family of circles of the same radius a , located in a plane perpendicular to this curve (fig 1).

FIG. 1. The knotted torus

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III. MAGNETIC FIELD AND PRESSURE

Circular coils, centered on the main curve, are traversed by a constant current, generating inside this chamber a magnetic field which gives the general shape of this curve. In each straight section of the chamber the magnetic field varies transversely as in an unknotted torus. Let $R(s)$ the local value of the radius of curvature and call $\hat{\mathbf{t}}(s)$ the tangent vector to the surface. The approximate value of the magnetic field at this point is :

$$\mathbf{B}(r, \theta, s) \approx \frac{\mu_0 I}{2\pi R(s)} \hat{\mathbf{t}}(s) \quad (2)$$

Consider a curve $\gamma(s)$ running along the surface of a tube of constant radius a around the node. Such a curve can be constructed with zero torsion (non-spiral), for example by following a constant longitudinal circle in the Frenet basis $\{ \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{b} \}$:

$$\gamma(s) = \mathbf{r}(s) + a \cos(\phi) \mathbf{n}(s) + a \sin(\phi) \mathbf{b}(s) \quad (3)$$

ϕ being a constant angle. This curve remains on the surface, without helical winding.

The magnetic pressure is :

$$p_B = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} \quad (4)$$

and the pressure gradient, along the $\gamma(s)$ curve, is :

$$\frac{dp_B}{ds} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} B \frac{dB}{ds} \quad (5)$$

as $B(s) \approx 1/R(s)$:

$$\frac{dB}{ds} \approx \frac{1}{R_s^2} \frac{dR}{ds} \Rightarrow \left| \frac{dp_B}{ds} \right| \approx \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{1}{R_s} \left| \frac{dR}{ds} \right| \quad (6)$$

The gradient will be maximal where the curvature :

$$\kappa(s) = \frac{1}{R(s)} \quad (7)$$

changes rapidly, And the variation dR/ds is strong, typically at points where the knot turns abruptly (such as at the transition from the upper lobe to the lower lobe).

For the trefoil knot, these points correspond to angles $t \approx 0, 2\pi/3, 4\pi/3$, where the curvature is maximal. The relative variations of the local value of the curvature at the wall are of the same order as that observed in the trefoil knot, i.e. 3. We therefore have an amplitude of variation of the pressure, along the curve $\gamma(s)$ of the order of 9. This natural variation of the gradient, due to the topology, means that it is not necessary, as in the ordinary torus of tokamak, to create a helical circulation of the plasma using a poloidal field created by induction.

IV. CONCLUSION

The knotted torus geometry offers an elegant alternative to the stellarator. It uses the topology of the magnetic field as a confinement mechanism, without the need for exotic components or heavy numerical optimization. It deserves further exploration as a next-generation fusion architecture.